

LEARNING STYLES AND WAY OF GETTING KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the typology of a hypotaxeme(a complex sentence) with an adverbial clause of causality and its constant features in more than 80 languages of the world, which allowed the author to reveal certain typological characteristics of the mentioned hypotaxeme, mainly its universal, frequental and implicative laws of structural-semantic organization and functional usage.

Keywords: hypotaxeme, adverbial clause of causality, constant features, universal, frequental and implicative features, structural-semantic organization, functional usage.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Teaching is one of those careers where you learn something new every day, and many educators cite this as one of the main things they hope to get out of their career.

On a strictly professional level, the education you attain to become a teacher opens your eyes to many things you may never have been exposed to before. Pursuing a degree in education teaches you so much about learning itself: pedagogy, methodology, etc. You learn how people learn and how to best teach students. Additionally, so many other elements go into teaching that the process of becoming an educator in itself teaches you a great deal. No matter what you teach, your knowledge in many fields will deepen and expand. Then there's the question of the teacher credentialing process which is also a learning experience.

Teachers also learn a great deal about themselves through teaching. Teaching requires you to step out of yourself in a way you may have never done before, and through this you learn about yourself as a teacher and as a person. You may learn more about how you work with others, particularly with children, and better understand how to communicate effectively and teach efficiently. You can learn how to better handle stress, and the organizational skills you'll gain from planning lessons and grading assignments will be invaluable. Furthermore, many teachers say the lessons they learn from their own students are the ones that make the job so fulfilling. Students bring a lot of their own life experiences to the classroom, and some of the things they have to say will enlighten you in ways you might not expect. Hearing your students out when they want to voice their opinions can

broaden your perspective. LEARNING STYLES ARE ALSO IMPORTANT FOR TEACHERS

One of the most accepted understandings of learning styles is that student learning styles fall into three categories: Visual Learners, Auditory Learners and Kinesthetic Learners. These learning styles are found within educational theorist Neil Fleming's VARK model of Student Learning. VARK is an acronym that refers to the four types of learning styles: Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing Preference, and Kinesthetic. (The VARK model is also referred to as the VAK model, eliminating Reading/Writing as a category of preferential learning.) The VARK model acknowledges that students have different approaches to how they process information, referred to as "preferred learning modes." The main ideas of VARK are outlined in Learning Styles Again: VARKing up the right tree! (Fleming & Baume, 2006)

- Students' preferred learning modes have significant influence on their behavior and learning.
- Students' preferred learning modes should be matched with appropriate learning strategies.
- Information that is accessed through students' use of their modality preferences shows an increase in their levels of comprehension, motivation, and metacognition.

Identifying your students as visual, auditory, reading/writing, kinesthetic, learners, and aligning your overall curriculum with these learning styles, will prove to be beneficial for your entire classroom. Keep in mind, sometimes you may find that it's a combination of all three sensory modalities that may be the best option. Allowing students to access information in terms they are comfortable with will increase their academic confidence.

Visual

Visual learners prefer the use of images, maps, and graphic organizers to access and understand new information.

Auditory

Auditory learners best understand new content through listening and speaking in situations such as lectures and group discussions. Aural learners use repetition as a study technique and benefit from the use of mnemonic devices.

Read & Write

Students with a strong reading/writing preference learn best through words. These students may present themselves as copious note takers or avid readers, and are able to translate abstract concepts into words and essays.

Kinesthetic

Students who are kinesthetic learners best understand information through tactile representations of information. These students are hands-on learners and

learn best through figuring things out by hand (i.e. understanding how a clock works by putting one together).

By understanding what kind of learner you and/or your students are, you can now gain a better perspective on how to implement these learning styles into your lesson plans and study techniques.

The term “learning styles” speaks to the understanding that every student learns differently. Technically, an individual’s learning style refers to the preferential way in which the student absorbs, processes, comprehends and retains information. For example, when learning how to build a clock, some students understand the process by following verbal instructions, while others have to physically manipulate the clock themselves. This notion of individualized learning styles has gained widespread recognition in education theory and classroom management strategy. Individual learning styles depend on cognitive, emotional and environmental factors, as well as one’s prior experience. In other words: everyone’s different. It is important for educators to understand the differences in their students’ learning styles, so that they can implement best practice strategies into their daily activities, curriculum and assessments. Many degree programs, specifically higher level ones like a doctorate of education, integrate different learning styles and educational obstacles directly into program curriculum.

Swot Strategies

Referred to as SWOT (“Study Without Tears”), Flemings provides advice on how students can use their learning modalities and skills to their advantage when studying for an upcoming test or assignment.

Visual SWOT Strategies

- Utilize graphic organizers such as charts, graphs, and diagrams.
- Redraw your pages from memory.
- Replace important words with symbols or initials.
- Highlight important key terms in corresponding colors.

Aural SWOT Strategies

• Record your summarized notes and listen to them on tape.
• Talk it out. Have a discussion with others to expand upon your understanding of a topic.

- Reread your notes and/or assignment out loud.
- Explain your notes to your peers/fellow “aural” learners.

Read/Write SWOT Strategies

- Write, write and rewrite your words and notes.
- Reword main ideas and principles to gain a deeper understanding.
- Organize diagrams, charts, and graphic organizers into statements.

Kinesthetic SWOT Strategies

- Use real life examples, applications and case studies in your summary to help with abstract concepts.

- Redo lab experiments or projects.

- Utilize pictures and photographs that illustrate your idea.

- The term **teaching method** refers to the general principles, pedagogy and management strategies used for classroom instruction.

- Your choice of teaching method depends on what fits you – your educational philosophy, classroom demographic, subject area(s) and school mission statement.

- Teaching theories can be organized into four categories based on two major parameters: a teacher-centered approach versus a student-centered approach, and high-tech material use versus low-tech material use.

- **Teacher-Centered Approach to Learning**

- Taken to its most extreme interpretation, teachers are the main authority figure in a teacher-centered instruction model. Students are viewed as “empty vessels”[External link:open in new](#) who passively receive knowledge from their teachers through lectures and direct instruction, with an end goal of positive results from testing and assessment. In this style, teaching and assessment are viewed as two separate entities; student learning is measured through objectively scored tests and assessments.

- [Learn more about the different teaching styles that use a teacher-centered approach.](#)

- **Student-Centered Approach to Learning**

- While teachers are still an authority figure in a student-centered teaching model, teachers and students play an equally active role in the learning process.

- The teacher’s primary role is to coach and facilitate student learning and overall comprehension of material, and to measure student learning through both formal and informal forms of assessment, like group projects, student portfolios, and class participation. In the student-centered classroom, teaching and assessment are connected because student learning is continuously measured during teacher instruction.

- [Learn more about the different teaching styles that use a student-centered approach](#)

Personalized Learning is such a new educational model that its definition is still evolving. At the heart of the model, teachers have students follow personalized learning plans that are specific to their interests and skills. Student self-direction and choice in the curriculum are hallmarks of personalized learning.

Assessment is also tailored to the individual: schools and classrooms that implement personalized learning use competency-based progression, so that students can move onto the next standards or topics when they’ve mastered what

they're currently working on. That way, students in personalized learning classrooms can progress to work beyond their grade level as they master topics, while students who need additional help have that time built into their daily schedules as well.

There's also room for an emphasis on college and career readiness in personalized learning environments. Students who don't require remediation or extension work can instead work with teachers to nurture social skills and other or 21st-century skills lessons and receive mentoring.

Personalized learning is extremely student centered, but teachers are required to teach lessons, look at frequent assessment data, and meet with students to make any necessary changes to their learning plans. They'll also need to have a certain comfort level with technology: the differentiated and personalized instruction that students receive often come in the form of online lessons and programs, so teachers must be able to navigate virtual platforms with ease.

There are various ways you can assess your learning abilities and determine what learning style best suits your needs. Here are a few tips to consider when trying to identify your personal learning style:

Take an assessment. There are various assessments available online through which you can identify your learning style based on the guidelines of different theories.

Experiment with different learning methods. It may be helpful for you to experiment with learning the same materials through different methods to determine what style best suits your needs.

Reflect on your learning experiences. You can consider your past learning experiences and think about what methods of acquiring knowledge have been most successful for you over time.